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Evidence of accomplishment

Report

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1. Summary

This document was created as part of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project. One of the specific objectives of the ASTRAL project is to map the distribution of pollutants of emerging concern in the selected IMTA open water labs, focusing on the application of robust and reliable sampling, sample preparation and analysis methods to be used to establish routinary monitoring plans in such type of aquaculture production facilities. The deliverable's scope and objectives include the development of an *ad hoc* large volumes water microplastics sampling device, application in the ASTRAL selected IMTA labs, the application of the best available sample preparation and analysis technology. Furthermore, this deliverable aims at describing recommendations for improvement and plans to define a routine monitoring plan for the aquaculture related MicroPlastic (MP) pollution fingerprint assessment.

2. Objectives of the deliverable

ASTRAL will analyse the presence of microplastics, an emerging pollutant that could affect the production as well as the quality of the products, in the environment around the IMTA facilities. To mitigate risks related to these threats, ASTRAL will suggest specific monitoring programmes for each IMTA lab, considering the regional specificities. The most appropriate technologies and sampling strategies will be considered for addressing specifically the identified risks. The ultimate purpose of the deliverable is to:

- Recommend strategies for improvement: Actionable recommendations for improvement that can be implemented to enhance the technology's performance.
- Suggest an implementation plan: the deliverable will outline a plan for implementing the recommended improvements, including timelines, resource allocation, and any necessary changes to processes or systems.

3. Background

At global level, there the ambition to intensify aquaculture production to fulfil a growing demand. As the demand has grown, the number of aquaculture facilities has increased, and existing locations have expanded. Considering the productions systems, the farms and production lines, the aquaculture industry benefits from a diversity of synthetic materials. Synthetic ropes offer lower weight and greater strength and durability than natural fibres, and are easier to handle, compared to their natural counterparts. Most modern aquaculture activities use plastic-based lines, cages or nets suspended from buoyant or submergible structures (in part made of plastic) as well as nanotech plastic-based anti-biofouling agents and paints. Tanks, pens, nets, floats and pontoons as well as the pipes of the fish feed supplying systems and feed itself are made of plastic material. Plastic materials within aquaculture sites are maintained and controlled for chemical degradation, biofouling and corrosion, with regular inspections to ensure strength and stability. Lost gear, broken and fragmented equipment, and release of MP debris because of intense use have been suggested as sources of both macro and microplastic emissions from aquaculture at both the global and local level. The level of contribution from direct release of MPs during production procedures remains a knowledge gap that needs to be filled. Europe and Norway are responsible to counteract marine

waste and agreed on implementing the UN sustainability goals, especially SDG 14 “Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development”. SDG 14 is also repeated in the Directive (EU) 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/904/oj>). Furthermore, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive requests that the amount and composition of marine waste does not cause harm to marine and coastal environments. However, neither amounts of plastics nor the hazards posed by plastics and microplastics in the environment are fully understood. Standardized methods for sample preparation, analysis and quantification of MPs do not yet exist, hampering the comparison of results between studies. Visual identification approaches using morphological criteria alone have often led to significant errors, which underlines the importance of using chemical identification. The present deliverable documents the utility and sensitivity of current methods, and as such contributes to the background and knowledge base needed for the establishment of international monitoring programs for microplastic.

4. Case studies description

4.1 IMTA lab in Ireland

The site is within a sheltered enclosed area to the east of Bertraghboy Bay (figure 1). The study area is predominantly shallow with low current flows. Current speeds and directions are measured using two Valeport Midas ECM current meters which were deployed over a 15-day period near the test site at an average of 9.6 m and 15 m water depths. The resulting scatter chart for the timeseries of midwater and seabed currents are given in figure 2. The mean current speeds during the sampling were 0.040 and 0.028 m/s for mid water and seabed respectively, and residual currents and directions were 0.028 m/s at 171°N and 0.015 m/s at 180°N for mid water and seabed respectively. As such these parameters are indicative of a location with low current flow and little dispersive capacity for fish cage waste. Based on the dialog with the IMTA facility manager, any discharge from the cages at this site is likely to be dispersed initially to the south and any particulate wastes would likely be deposited on the seabed close to the cages. Furthermore, the tidal range is of approx. 5m. The salinity ranges from 24 to 35 ppt but is typically >32 ppt while the water temperature ranges from 5 to 18 °C.

Figure 1 - Location of the sampling sites at Lehanagh Pool, in Bertraghboy Bay, Connemara, Co. Galway, Ireland. 1 1: Farm "MI IMTA centre"; 2: S-Farm "MI IMTA south" and 3: Reference site "MI Ref".

Based on the bathymetry orientation of the surface and bottom currents, three sampling sites were identified for water sampling (Table 1). Every plastic and workwear used by the sampling operators was documented separately and stored in the ASTRAL data archive.

Figure 2 – Scatter chart of timeseries for mid water and seabed current in Lehanagh Pool IMTA site (Ireland).

Table 1 – Description of the sampling sites within the Irish case study, Lehanagh Pool, in Bertraghboy Bay, Ireland.

Sample label	Description	Date	Time UTC	Latitude	Longitude
MI IMTA centre	Center of grid at Lehanagh Pool	11.03.2022, 16.03.2022 16.03.2022	11:15 12:30 15:02	53.400638	-9.819444
MI IMTA south	Close to estuary for the river Gowla.	11.03.2022, 16.03.2022 16.03.2022	12:08 13:22 15:44	53.390151	-9.808571
MI Ref	Outer channel of entrance to Cashel Bay	11.03.2022, 16.03.2022 16.03.2022	12:51 14:02 16:24	53.389057	-9.844510
MI MP-B	Blank; autoclaved deionized water	11.03.2022, 16.03.2022 16.03.2022	11:15 - 12:51 12:38 - 14:02 15:02 - 16:24		

Furthermore, a plastic material inventory was run to map the use of different polymers within the aquaculture production (Table 2).

Table 2- Plastic material inventory at Lehanagh Pool IMTA.

Item	Material	Use
Rope	Nylon	Secure farm grid
Lines	Polypropylene	Provide cultivation space
Floats & buoys	Polystyrene	For deployment of growing lines
Cable Ties	Polyamide Nylon 6/6	Connecting grid and riser
Work Clothing	PVC, Nylon, Polyester	connecting grid to cushion buoy

Work Gloves	rubber, nylon?	providing buoyancy to grid
Rope	Nylon	shellfish grow-out structure
Lines	Polypropylene	keeps seaweed growing in line at desired depth during grow-out

4.2 IMTA in Scotland

The Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) in Oban operates an experimental low-trophic aquaculture farm in Port-a-Bhuiltin on the Scottish west coast (figure 3). The total lease area of 30 hectares currently hosts one production site; a submerged grid system of 100m x 100m (equaling 1 hectare production space). The site provides cultivation space for a variety of seaweed but also shellfish species while focusing on endemic species of economic as well as ecological relevance such as brown seaweeds i.e. kelp (*Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima*, *Laminaria digitata*), European flat oysters (*Ostrea edulis*), and King scallops (*Pecten maximus*). This is an open coastal aquaculture site, situated approximately 250m away from the mainland coast, experiencing average surface current speeds of 11 cm s^{-1} predominantly in NE-SW or 160° direction. Whilst average current speed can be considered moderate, it can vary between as little as 0.1 to as much as 550 cm s^{-1} across the year, being influenced by diurnal tides, wind and wave regimes. Annual variation in sea surface temperature ranges from 6 to 15°C and for salinity from 24 to 34ppt although typically above 32ppt .

Figure 3 - Location of the sampling sites at Port-a-Bhuiltin aquaculture farm, Scotland. 1: S-Farm; 2: N-Farm and 3: Reference site.

Based on the bathymetry orientation of the surface and bottom currents, three sampling sites were identified for water sampling (Table 3). The gear used by the sampling operators was documented separately and stored in the ASTRAL data archive.

Table 3 - Description of the sampling sites within the Scottish case study, Port-a-Bhuiltin aquaculture farm, Scotland.

Sample label	Description	Date	Time UTC	Latitude	Longitude
SAMS MP 001-1	S-Farm; Ebb flow	04.05.2022	11:33	56,4882	-5,4713
SAMS MP 002-1	N-Farm; Ebb flow	04.05.2022	13:05	56,4888	-5,4707
SAMS MP 003-1	Ref Site; Ebb flow	04.05.2022	13:50	56,4884	-5,4744
SAMS MP 001-2	S-Farm; Flood flow	04.05.2022	14:35	56,4882	-5,4713
SAMS MP 002-2	N-Farm; Flood flow	04.05.2022	15:24	56,4888	-5,4707
SAMS MP 003-2	Ref Site; Flood flow	05.05.2022	10:05	56,4884	-5,4744
SAMS MP-B	Blank; autoclaved deionized water				

Furthermore, a plastic material inventory was run to map the use of different polymers within aquaculture production (Table 4).

Table 4 - Plastic material inventory at Port-a-Bhuiltin aquaculture farm.

Item	# units used in the IMTA	Material	Use
Anchor Line	12	polypropylene rope	Secure farm grid
Grid Line	12	polypropylene	Provide cultivation space
Trawl Float	72	Compressed polystyrene	Supports grid line and growing line attachment
Grid Riser Rope	72	Polypropylene	For deployment of growing lines
prusik	72	Nylon	Connecting grid and riser
rope riser to cushion buoy	8	Polypropylene	Connecting grid to cushion buoy
Cushion Buoy	8	foam-filled oceanic cushion	Providing buoyancy to grid
Oyster Basket	4	high-density polyethylene (HDPE)	Shellfish grow-out structure
Trawl Float	96	Compressed polystyrene	Keeps seaweed growing in line at desired depth during grow-out
Float/Weight Connection	96	Nylon	
Trawl Float Rope	96	Polypropylene	
Seaweed Growing Line	48	Polypropylene	
Twine	48	Polyester	seaweed deployment structure used in indirect seeding
Special Mark Buoy	2	Marine grade (UV stabilised) polyethylene.	

5. Materials and methods

5.1 Sampling strategy during the ASTRAL project

Microplastic sampling can be conducted using pumps, a strategy already used by scientists around the world, which enables the development of sampling methods that yield comparable results. Pump sampling can be conducted both from commercial and research vessels as well as from stationary and mobile vehicles inland. The smaller the size of the mesh, the smaller the particle size of the collected MPs. The mesh can be blocked by algae or organisms if the aperture size becomes small. However,

when the aperture size was increased, the toxic and small plastic particles may not be collected. In the aquatic environment, the depth of the water should be considered for sampling, and it is generally acknowledged that the abundance of MP surface is higher than that from water depth of 1–2 m. The used trawl nets varied between sampling depths. Samples from surface water used trawl-type sampling devices such as Manta trawl. Bongo nets for mid-water samples and benthic trawls for deeper water from the bottom layer were applied. Typically, the mesh apertures most commonly used for the net are 333–335 μm . In the ASTRAL project a compact, large volume microplastics sampling device is developed by NORCE staff (figure 4), delivered to the IMTA sites and locally operated by assigned personnel.

Figure 4 – Large Volumes Microplastics Sampling device engineered by NORCE for ASTRAL project. (Credit: Alessio Gomiero)

A large volume of seawater is conveyed by a large pump unit to a cascade of two stainless steel filters of a mesh size designed to trap particles (including plastic fragments in the micron range). After each sampling session the stainless-steel filters can be easily released from the filter holder unit and transferred to pre-cleaned glass petri dishes of an appropriate size (\varnothing 180 mm), sealed, kept in dark conditions and stored in a freezer at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Stored samples were grouped and shipped to the lab for the sample preparation and analysis by post or courier.

Furthermore, samples of the plastic material used within the IMTA lab facility have been requested to map the use of different polymers within the aquaculture production.

5.2 Instrument description

The sampling system consists of a pumping unit and a filtration unit, containing two filter holders. Figure 5 shows the schematic drawing of the system.

Figure 5 - Schematic drawing of the microplastics sampling device.

The filtration unit consists of two interconnected chambers where the top chamber holds the single-use 300 µm mesh stainless steel filter while the bottom chamber holds the single-use 10 µm mesh stainless steel filter. The preparation of the filter holders before the sampling session starts with the opening of the filtration chambers.

5.3- Sampling & samples preparation

5.3.1- Sampling at IMTA Ireland

The sampling session took place in August 2022.

For the water sampling, approximately 500 L of water has been collected from each of three sampling sites located in the IMTA's facility (table 5).

Table 5 - Recorded volumes of seawater in the two sampling stations at the Irish IMTA managed by the Marine Institute.

Sample code	Location description	Collected volume (L)	Note
MI IMTA centre	MI - IMTA centre	585	
MI IMTA south	MI - IMTA south	590	

MI Ref	MI - Ref	531	
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After each filtration session each filter was placed in pre cleaned large glass petri dishes, sealed and stored in cold and dark conditions prior to shipment to NORCE partner Plastlab. The sample's preparation method applies a gentle and efficient purification step before quantitative chemical identification. The main interferences for a reliable quantification are the residual organic components that may create a high background signal during analysis, hampering a correct MP quantification. The principle used is a sequential enzymatic degradation and removal of proteins and fats followed by a strong oxidation treatment and enhanced dissolution of fats in an alkaline environment. Once in the ultraclean plastic lab the stainless-steel filters were removed from the container and placed on a large crystallizer filled with 5% Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS) and placed on orbital shaking motion and incubated at 50°C for a minimum of 6 hours before further enzymatic treatments. After incubation in SDS, the sample was sonicated to release the particles from the filtering surface and transferred quantitatively to a vacuum filtration assembly and passed through a 10 µm stainless steel filter. The funnel was rinsed with a 50% ethanol/water solution from a PTFE squeeze bottle to ensure complete transfer. The filter and sample were placed back into the beaker (inverted), and glycine buffer was added. Ultrasonication was performed on the sample beaker for 5 minutes to release any particles attached to the filter. Following ultrasonication, the filter was rinsed with 1 mL of GF/A filtered Milli-Q water to transfer any remaining microplastics to the sample beaker. Then, 1 mL of protease enzyme was added, and the beaker was incubated at 50°C for 48 hours. For the final purification step, a strong oxidative digestion was performed using 30% hydrogen peroxide at 50°C for 6 hours. The sample reduced into a clear liquid. The filtration and sonication steps were repeated, and after sonication, the filter was thoroughly rinsed on both sides with 50% ethanol/water. Any remaining ethanol/water solution in the sample beaker was evaporated at 50°C until 1 mL of solution remained. The 1 mL of sample was transferred to a glass vial for storage, and the tube was washed with 4 x 1 mL of 50% ethanol, resulting in a final volume of 5 mL in the sample vial. Prior to analysis, the contents were filtered onto a 0.1 µm Anodisc filter (Whatman, Φ 13 mm) and dried at room temperature in a glass petri dish with a lid until further examination.

5.3.2- Sampling at IMTA Scotland

The sampling session took place in May 2022.

For the water sampling, approximately 500 L of water has been collected from each of three sampling sites located in the IMTA's facility (table 6).

Table 6 - Recorded volumes of seawater in the two sampling stations at the Scottish IMTA managed by the SAMS Institute.

Sample code	Location description	Collected volume (L)	Note
SAMS MP 001-1	North of IMTA - replicate 1	591	
SAMS MP 002-1	South of IMTA – replicate 1	580	
SAMS MP 003-1	Ref site replicate 1	571	
SAMS MP 001-2	North of IMTA - replicate 2	567	

SAMS MP 002-2	South of IMTA – replicate 2	561	
SAMS MP 003-2	Ref site replicate 2	567	

5.4-Analysis

5.4.1 Identification of MPs by vibrational spectroscopy: μ FTIR

Identification of plastic fragments > 500 μ m was performed using an Attenuated total reflectance (ATR) coupled with Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy using a Thermo Fisher Nicolet iN10 MX microscope. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy is utilized for identifying chemical compounds, studying molecular structures, examining surface properties by contact and without further preparation. It utilizes total internal reflection to generate an evanescent wave that penetrates the sample, providing valuable molecular information.

Identification of polymer types and measurement of particle sizes $10 > X > 300 \mu$ m were performed using Micro Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (Thermo Fisher Nicolet iN10 MX Infrared Imaging Microscope). The instrument is equipped with a N₂-cooled 64x64 line array mapping detector and a quantum MCT (mercury cadmium telluride) detector. The linear array detector collected 4 scans /acquisition point per time, and the IR spectra of each microplastic particle were recorded in the mid-IR range of 4000-850 cm^{-1} , with a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} in transmission mode. Polymer identification was performed by comparing the spectral match of the particles with a reference library (SiMPle, v1.3.1 β). Polymers with a spectral match greater than 70% were considered positively identified. The software used for identification and grouping of polymer types also facilitated the theoretical mass calculations per particle. Four morphotypes (fiber, pellet, film and fragment) of MPs were classified. The relevant polymer groups identified in this study were Polypropylene (PP), Polyethylene (PE), Polyester (PES), Polystyrene (PS), Polyurethane (PU), Nylon or Polyamide (PA), and Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA), acrylic paint, Polyvinyl alcohol (PVOH), Cellulose ester (CE) and Polyether sulfones (PES). Due to the high content of back carbon, a material which adsorb completely in the Infra-Red spectral range, in the formulation the occurrence of tyre wear particles in the samples cannot be detected by such technique but through pyrolysis mass spectrometry (pyr-GCMS).

5.4.2 Thermal degradation analysis: Pyr-GCMS

Pyrolysis Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (Pyr-GCMS) is a destructive method that uses thermal decomposition of materials at elevated temperatures in an inert (low-oxygen) atmosphere. Large molecules break at their weakest bonds, producing smaller, more volatile fragments. These fragments can be separated by gas chromatography and detected by a mass spectrometer and the output data can be used as a fingerprint to identify material. The obtained pyrograms, with peaks of ions appearing at different retention times, are compared with a customized database and cross-checked with literature to identify the chemical composition of the material using recommendations and selection criteria from Fischer and Scholz-Böttcher (2017) and Gomiero et al. (2019).

Nine of the most commonly used plastic polymers are quantified: polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyamide (PA6), polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), polycarbonate (PC), polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polyurethane (PU). Additionally, differently from the FTIR technique, pyr-GCMS is able to estimate the content of tyre particles in the samples by characterizing the occurrence of styrene-butadiene rubber.

Standard curves with known concentrations are used to calculate the concentrations of target materials in the sample. Pyr-GCMS analyses were performed with a Shimadzu Optima 2010C GCMS equipped with a Rxi-5ms column (RESTEC, Bellefonte, PA) and coupled with Frontier Laboratories Multi-Shot Pyrolyzer EGA/PY-3030D with auto-shot sampler.

In this analysis a Limit of Quantification (LOQ) of $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for most of the addressed polymers, and $2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PMMA and PC was estimated. The lower size of the analysed plastic particles depends on the filter size used in the sample preparation steps. For the present study stainless steel filters of $10 \mu\text{m}$ size were used. Aliquots of MP stored in the ethanol/water solution were filtered on pre-burned GF/C 25mm fiberglass filters. The obtained filters are folded in a pyrolysis cup for chemical analysis. During the pyr-GCMS analyses dust trap collectors were used to evaluate possible contamination from airborne particles. Furthermore, the steel cups used for the pyrolysis analysis were cleaned before use with a butane blow torch at 1400°C to remove any plastic.

5.5-Data treatment

5.5.1 QA/QC -Exclusion of potential contamination

To assess and address potential contamination, samples were examined and evaluated against the results of the wet traps analysis and reporting the correspondence of samples with positive microplastic identifications.

5.5.2 Microplastic particle concentration - μ -FTIR

The concentration of microplastic particles (MP) was calculated in number of plastic particles (MPS) per cubic meter of samples water using the SiMPLe software output. Data are stored in Microsoft Excel based environment. The number of detected MP particles is standardized to 1m^3 of water.

5.5.3 Microplastic particle concentration – pyr GCMS

The concentration of microplastic particles (MP) was calculated in number of plastic particles (MPS) per cubic meter of samples water using the estimated mass per particle obtained from the MPS 2.0 (Lab Frontiers) software output, and the wet weight of the sample at the time of dissection.

$$\text{MP Concentration} = (\text{Particle mass (mg)}) / (\text{Sample volume (m}^3\text{)})$$

5.5 Collection of model data relevant for analysing dispersion of buoyant particular matter

A brief literature search has been performed, looking for data and results relevant for the two locations studied in this work package. Local wind measurements from Mace Head were collected as provided online by Met Éireann, the Irish Meteorological service. For the Scotland site, the wind data from Dunstaffnage were collected from the Met Office Integrated Data Archive System (MIDAS) online service. Both sites are also covered in downscaled modeling products that are available. The Irish Marine Institute provided us with 3 years of 50m resolution data covering the Bertraghboy bay with a temporal resolution of three hours (Nagy et al, 2021). For the Scotland case the surface data covering the Loch Linnhe and nearby sub loch's from a sub region were collected from of the WeStCOMS hydrodynamic model system, provided by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS). This is a high resolution FVCOM-based model for western Scotland (Aleynik et al, 2016). The WeStCOMS data was interpolated onto a regular 50x50m resolution grid. The velocity data was averaged over three years, for each season. As the time resolution were 3 hours, there is some risk of aliasing in the regions

with very dominant and energetic tides, but we still believe the directions will be informative in most areas.

6 -Results

6.1 Contamination monitoring

Three procedural blanks and six samples from the wet dust trap collectors were analyzed to monitor potential sources of contamination affecting the sample preparation and the analysis. The contamination was related to handling the sampling equipment, preparing the sample for analysis, and finally the analysis itself. The results showed a contamination of 6.0 ± 1.0 MPs per procedural blank sample. The polymeric composition of the contaminating MPs was $\approx 50\%$ Polyethylene- PE, $\approx 30\%$ Poly ethyl sulfone - PES and $\approx 20\%$ Polypropylene-PP. The measured contamination of non-synthetic materials (approximately 22 ± 5 particles) was protein-based material and cellulose fibres. Furthermore, the result of the wet trap collectors showed a contamination of 2.9 ± 2.0 MPs per trap located in the clean lab where the samples were processed and analysed by μ -FTIR imaging. The polymeric composition of the wet trap collectors were $\approx 25\%$ PES, $\approx 25\%$ PE and $\approx 50\%$ Polystyrene - PS.

6.2 MPs observations IMTA Ireland

Overall, 20 MPs/m^3 were observed in the sample collected inside the Lehanagh Pool IMTA (IMTA Ir - Centre); 23 MPs/m^3 were observed in the sample collected south of the IMTA facility near the mouths of Gowla and Gowlabeg rivers and $16,9 \text{ MPs/m}^3$ were observed in the reference site (figure 6). A significant difference between both the sampling site inside the IMTA and the site south of the facility versus the reference ones. Overall, PP ($\approx 22\text{-}30\%$) followed by PE ($\approx 16\text{-}29\%$) and Polyamide - PA ($\approx 13\text{-}14\%$) are the three most distributed polymer types in the investigated area while the remaining detected polymer types (PS, Polyurethane- PU, Ethyl Vinyl Acetate- EVA, Polyamide- PA, Acrylic paint, Polyethylene terephthalate -PET, cellulose ester and Poly ethyl sulfone) accounted for a total of $\approx 30\%$. The relative abundance of these detected polymers significantly changes between the South sampling site and both the IMTA Ir – Centre site and the reference site while no significant difference is scored between the reference (figure 7). Furthermore, for the most predominant fractions, PP, PE and PA particles showed a main size distribution towards $11\text{--}30 \mu\text{m}$ sizes in the IMTA area while slightly larger particles dominate the most recurring size fraction in the reference site ($30\text{--}60 \mu\text{m}$; figure 8). From the perspective of MPs characteristics, only morphotypes of fiber and fragment were visualized the sample collected near the mouths of Gowla and Gowlabeg rivers show the most predominant fibres contribution ($\approx 75\%$) while both the reference and the site inside the Lehanagh Pool IMTA show a similar pattern of fibres/fragment distribution (figure 9).

Figure 6 – MPs distribution inside the IMTA (Ir-Centre), south of the IMTA facility (IMTA South) and in a reference area (IMTA-ref) the in the Irish IMTA.

Figure 7 – Polymers' relative abundance in the in the inside the IMTA (Ir-Centre), south of the IMTA facility (IMTA South) and in a reference area (IMTA-ref) the Irish IMTA.

Figure 8 – MPS grain size distribution on water samples collected in the Irish IMTA.

Figure 9 - Morphotypes presentation and proportion of MPs inside the IMTA (Ir-Centre), south of the IMTA facility (IMTA South) and in a reference area (IMTA-ref) of the Irish IMTA.

6.2.1 Back confirmation of microplastics occurrence by GCMS-pyr

The results of the vibrational spectroscopy oriented technique (μ -FTIR) are confirmed by the thermoanalytical assessment as all detectable polymers in the GCMS-pyr method were back detected. Total amount of polymers varied from 50 (Ir-Centre) to 62 (Ir-South) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PE, from 77 (ref) to 109 (Ir-South) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PP, from 10 (Ref) to 13 Ir-Centre) $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ of PA, from < 1 (Ir-South) to 11 (Ir-Centre) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PU, from 10 (Ir-Centre) to 15 (ref) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of Pls (Polyester; table. 7).

Table 7 – Occurrence of plastic polymers inside the IMTA (Ir-Centre), south of the IMTA facility (IMTA South) and in a reference area (IMTA-ref) of the Irish IMTA as detected by the GCMS-pyr technique.

Sample	Polymer type ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)										Sum
	PE	PP	PS	PVC	PA	PMMA	PC	Pls	PU	SBR	
Ir centre	50	90	< 1	< 1	13	< 2	< 1	10	11	< 1	228
Ir South	62	109	< 1	< 1	9	< 2	< 1	10	< 1	< 1	281
Ir Ref.	565	77	< 1	< 1	10	< 2	< 1	15	5	< 1	207
	Polymer type ($\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$)										
	PE	PP	PS	PVC	PA	PMMA	PC	PET	PU	SBR	
Prosedural Control	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 2	< 2	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	
Dust trap Control	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 2	< 2	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	
GCMS Room Control	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 2	< 2	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	

6.3. MPs observations in IMTA Scotland

Overall, 19 MPs/m³ were observed in the sample collected south of Port-a-Bhuiltin IMTA (SAMS MP-1), 21 MPs/m³ were observed in the sample collected north of the IMTA facility (SAMS MP-2) and 20 MPs/m³ were observed in the reference site (figure 10). No significant difference between the sampling sites were observed. Overall, PE (\approx 18- 27%) followed by PP (\approx 18-25 %) and PA (\approx 9-18 %) are the three most distributed polymer types in the investigated area while the remaining detected polymer types (PS, PU, EVA, PA, PLN, acrylic paint, PET cellulose ester and PES) accounted for a total of \approx 35 %. By the exception of PU which was not detected in the reference site, the relative abundance of the detected polymers does not change significantly across the investigated sampling sites (figure 11). For the most predominant fractions, PP, PE and PA particles showed a main size distribution towards 11–30 μ m sizes in all sampled sites (figure 12). From the perspective of MPs characteristics, only morphotypes of fibres and fragment were visualized. The samples show a slight predominancy of fibres versus particles morphotype (figure 13).

Figure 10 – MPs distribution south of the Port-a-Bhuiltin IMTA (SAMS MP-1), north of the IMTA facility (SAMS MP-2) and in a reference area (SAMS MP-3).

Figure 11 – Polymers’ relative abundance south of Port-a-Bhuiltin IMTA (SAMS MP-1), North of the IMTA facility (SAMS -MP2) and in a reference area (SAMS MP-3).

Figure 12 – MPS grain size distribution on water samples collected in the Scottish IMTA.

Figure 13 - Morphotypes presentation and proportion of MPs south the Port-a-Bhuiltin IMTA (SAMS MP-1), north of the IMTA facility (SAMS -MP2) and in a reference area (SAMS MP-3).

The results of the vibrational spectroscopy oriented technique (μ -FTIR) are confirmed by the thermoanalytical assessment as all detectable polymers in the GCMS-pyr method were back detected. Total amount of polymers varied from 40 (SAMS MP-1) to 45 (SAMS MP-3) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PE, from 27 (SAMS MP-3) to 30 (SAMS MP-1) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PP, from 4 (SAMS MP-3) to 8 (SAMS MP-1) $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ of PA, from 1 (SAMS MP-3) to 2 (SAMS MP-1) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of Pls, from < 1 (SAMS MP-2) to 5 (SAMS MP-1) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of PU and finally from 34 to 41 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of SBR in SAMS MP-3 and SAMS MP-2, respectively; table. 8).

Table 8 – Occurrence of plastic polymers south (SAMS MP1), north of the IMTA facility (SAMS MP2) and in a reference area (SAMS MP3) as detected by the GCMS-pyr technique.

Sample	Polymer type ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)										Sum
	PE	PP	PS	PVC	PA	PMMA	PC	Pls	PU	SBR	
SAMS MP-1	40	30	< 1	< 1	8	< 2	< 1	3	2	< 1	119
SAMS MP-2	42	29	< 1	< 1	5	< 2	< 1	5	< 1	< 1	122
SAMS MP-3	45	27	< 1	< 1	4	< 2	< 1	1	5	< 1	116
	Polymer type ($\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$)										
	PE	PP	PS	PVC	PA	PMMA	PC	PET	PU	SBR	
Procedural control	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 2	< 2	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	
Dust trap control	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 2	< 2	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	
GCMS room control	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 2	< 2	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	

7 Metocean considerations

Numerical ocean models can be essential tools for understanding and managing ecological parameters and pollutants (Hardesty et al, 2017). Models can predict how pollutants disperse over time, guide optimal sampling locations (JPI FACTS Project, 2021), and assimilate observational data. By exploring scenarios and detecting long-term trends, scientists can make informed recommendations for environmental conservation. These models bridge theory and practice, aiding sustainable practices and wildlife protection. The current project did not have a budget to perform particle or hydrodynamical model experiments around the two sites of interest but did allow for gathering and analysing a modest amount of data from state-of-the-art downscaled models, and get some insight into existing measurements from literature. The two models we describe combined with a particle model do however provide a unique potential for understanding the movements of particulate matter in these areas, due to the highly detailed representation of the coastlines and most important processes, spanning multiple years.

7.1 IMTA Ireland

Bertraghboy Bay, situated on the western coast of Ireland approximately 50 km west of Galway, spans a length of 12 km and gracefully opens towards the North Atlantic in the southwestern direction. This coastal expanse is characterized by the influence of pivotal oceanic currents, notably the North Atlantic Drift and the Irish Coastal Current, which exhibits a clockwise circulatory pattern around Ireland, as detailed in (Brown et al. 2003). These currents assume crucial roles in shaping the movement of marine debris beyond the bay's confines, over time there will be an exchange of matter between the open ocean and the bay, where the majority of matter received in the bay will come from the south, while the export of matter for the most part will travel north, and out into the North Atlantic Ocean. Within the bay itself, tidal movements and surface currents driven by wind predominantly govern the local hydrodynamics relevant for the movement of buoyant matter in the surface. Notably, the absence of major rivers is a distinctive feature, that combined with relatively shallow depths and strong winds leads to well mixed conditions in the vertical, although smaller rivers such as the Owenmore river, discharging on the north side, and the Owengowla river, with its outlet in the southeastern extremity of the bay, contribute to the aquatic landscape.

In Figure 14, can be observed the seasonal average wind roses at Mace Head for the years 2020 to 2022. The dominating directions are between the west and south for all seasons except spring. In this time period see a dominance from the east, although with significantly weaker winds than we see for fall and winter, when the strongest winds are experienced. Winds will affect the movements of and in the surface layer via two mechanisms, the direct drag of the surface and the phenomenon called Stokes Drift see e.g. (Bremer, 2017). Stokes Drift can be significant, up to 4% of the wind speed. (Kenyon, 1969). The movements due to both mechanisms will be in the direction of the wind, and depend on the amount of time the wind force is applied to a parcel of water, and the upwind open water distance (Fetch). Wave height, and hence Stokes drift, will depend directly on the length of the fetch, so particles on the surface of a south west facing bay like the Bertraghboy bay will tend to drift north east with wind directions similar to those presented here.

Figure 14- Bertraghboy Bay’s seasonal wind roses from Mace Head 2020-2022.

The seasonally averaged surface currents from a downscaled ocean model with 50m resolution are presented in the figure 15. We observe generally very weak currents in the shallow area near our site of interest, but that in the summer there is a tendency for southward direction currents, as we also observed in the short timeseries previously described in section 4.1 and shown in Figure 2. In all seasons there is a tendency for north easterly direction of currents, which is reasonable with regard to winds and the fact there are no major rivers discharging into the area. The orientation of the bay and the prevailing wind and current conditions means the bay might be prone to capture debris from the coastal current passing the mouth of the bay. The yearly survey by IBAL (Irish Business Against Litter) confirm that the south west facing beaches of Ireland are among the worst “black spots”, e.g. the Dogs Bay in the Wild Atlantic Way area on the north side of the entry to the Bertraghboy bay, have been marked as an “area of concern”, but the situation has improved after several years of cleaning efforts.

Figure 15 - Seasonally averaged surface currents in Bertraghboy Bay 2019-2021.

7.2 IMTA Scotland

Like the Irish bay, also the water systems around Loch Linnhe are to a large degree directly exposed to the Atlantic Ocean towards the southwest, and somewhat to the more protected Irish Sea to the south. Another similarity with the Irish site is that also here there is a persistent northward current on the outside of the loch mouth, the Scottish Coastal Current. Loch Linnhe has been extensively described (Taylor, 1997), as a complex sea-Loch system also including Lochs Eil, Leven, Creran, Etive, and O'Choire. The inner Lochs are separated from the outer loch by shallow sills. The sills are quite interesting to study as they can generate internal waves, vertical mixing, regulate deep water renewal, and more. The outer system differs from the Irish site mainly due to the relatively large freshwater discharge of rivers in the area and the larger depths. In (Taylor, 1997) daily average discharge rates from rivers Lochy and Nevis are described to be around 50 cubic meters per second and up to 400 cubic meters per second several times per year after major precipitation events. The effect of this is that the surface water is somewhat more brackish, and that there is a steady surface flow towards the open ocean of a few cm per second, also present in the measurements of (Edwards,2018), and at depths of approx 50m there is a weak inflow. This makes the circulation in this Loch quite similar to the large fjords in e.g. Norway. Wind roses from Dunstaffnage show modest winds compared to the Irish site, with wind from southwest being slightly more common than from the southeast, while winds from the north is rare (figure 16). Measurements of current west of Lismore (Edwards,2018) indicate that the surface layer of Loch Linnhe is driven by both tide, wind and precipitation, while the stronger currents at larger depths (15-50m) is tidally driven. The seasonal average current fields from the WeStCOMS model shown in Figure 17 to some degree correspond to observations, but we see the current speed is likely too high, this could be the result of aliasing error as previously mentioned, but the direction of the surface current is outward, as observations show. We also in some places see a tendency of currents to keep to the "right side" on the way out, which is very similar to the outflow of surface brackish water in Norwegian fjords.

As we understand the present data, the main consequence of the current conditions for a release of buoyant particles in the Loch is that particles will tend to leave the outer Lochs; a particle starting 50 km into the Loch moving outwards with an average speed of 5cm/s will leave in approximately 11 days. Sinking matter might however tend to move deeper into the Loch and possibly strand near the relatively shallow sills separating the inner Lochs from e.g. Linnhe. Since winds in this area is significantly weaker than the site at the west of Ireland, and the direction is less dominated by south-westerly winds, we speculate that surface matter from the Scottish Coastal Current will to a lesser degree move into and be trapped by the Loch system, which means stranded material are more likely to be of local origin, being transported around by winds and tidal currents.

Figure 16 - Seasonal wind roses for winter, spring, summer and autumn for the years 2020-2022 at Dunstaffnage.

Figure 17 - Seasonally averaged surface currents.

8 Literature comparison

A systematic literature review was performed to retrieve literature regarding the detection of MPs in aquaculture environment resulting from commonly used databases such as Google Scholar, Science Direct, Web of Science and PubMed. The obtained items were further refined to peer-reviewed research articles. The special keywords “microplastic and aquaculture” were applied as the key research criteria. 26 papers were extracted from the literature research. The reference list of each retrieved paper was also examined and retrieved when necessary. Overall, research articles about the detection of MPs in the aquaculture environment were involved in this literature comparison task. Published research regarding microplastics in global aquatic environments is increasing rapidly (Figure 18).

Figure 18 - Statistics of papers published on 'microplastics' and 'marine' since 2006 with citation numbers (Source: Wang et al., 2023).

Although aquatic environments are important to aquaculture productions, most of the studies only considered aquaculture activities as sources of microplastics in aquatic environments, without investigating microplastics in the aquaculture environments. Studies reporting microplastics detection in aquaculture environments and products remain limited (Miao et al., 2023). Due to the wide use of plastic products and the ubiquitous presence of microplastics, there is no doubt that all aquaculture systems are contaminated by microplastics. Researchers shows that the concentration of microplastics in aquaculture environments is generally higher than in surrounding environments because of rapidly expanding aquaculture activities (Cheng *et al.*, 2021). Microplastics can be released into aquaculture environments from plastic fishing gear as well as fish feed (Gomiero et al., 2020). In addition, geography, and weather influence microplastics accumulation and distribution in aquaculture environments (Cheng et al., 2021). Aquaculture areas are mostly enclosed or semi-enclosed aquatic environments, which prevent the transfer of microplastics to other areas, causing the accumulation of microplastics in the water column and sediment (Lusher et al., 2017). Aquaculture regions located in areas with high anthropogenic activities contribute substantially to the increase in microplastics observed environmentally and biologically. For instance, 16.4/m³ of microplastics were found in the mussel-farming region in Jurujuba Cove (Castro et al., 2016), while the total average abundance of microplastics in Xiangshan Bay was 8.9 ± 4.7 items/m³ in seawater and 1739 ± 2153 items/kg in sediment (Wu et al., 2020), while Kruger et al. (2020) found levels of microplastics ranging from 0 to 213 particles/kg dry weight in sediments collected from round three fish farms located at the Mediterranean coastline of Spain. In the mariculture zone of the Maowei Sea (Zhu et al., 2019), the abundances of microplastics range from 1.2 to 10.1 particles/L, and a mean value of 1594 ± 1352 particles/m³ of microplastics was found in the shrimp-culturing farm in Longjiao Bay (Chen et al., 2020). The microplastics in these studies appeared most as fibers, making this shape dominant component in the data. In the Ma'an Archipelago, fibers were the most dominant type of microplastics in both surface water (70.0 ± 27.0%) and sediment (92.0 ± 9.0%; Zhang et al., 2020b), while fibers accounted for 94.66% of microplastics in the surface water of Xiangshan Bay (Chen et al., 2018). Fiber microplastics in the environment predominantly originate from plastic textiles, such as cloth, fishing

nets and lines, the annual production of which reached 60 million metric tons (Acharya et al., 2021). In addition, fragments, films and granules in aquaculture environments come from the degradation of plastic products like plastic bags, bottles, containers, agricultural films, fishing gear. Pellets or microbeads mostly originate from primary microplastics, which are used in personal care products (toothpaste, facial scrubs and skin cleaners), domestic cleaning products, and medical and industrial applications; the foam widely used in packaging materials and fishing gear is also a source of microplastics in aquaculture environments (GESAMP, 2016). Regarding chemical composition, polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) were microplastics detected in these studies, because of their high production and wide application. The production of PP and PE accounted for 49% of global plastic products in 2018, including use in food packaging, plastic bags, bottles, containers, pipes, automotive parts, agricultural film, houseware, etc (Chioatto et al., 2023; Beghetto et al., 2023). Due to plastic’s wide use and improper waste management, microplastics eventually contaminate every facet of the human environment, including aquaculture.

Table 9 – Overview of the concentrations and characteristics of microplastics in different aquaculture systems.

Site	Source	Abundance	Size	Composition	ref
Xiangshan Bay, China	Seawater	8.9 ± 4.7 items/m ³	1.54 ± 1.53 mm.	PE, PP, PS, PA, PET, cellulose	Wu et al., 2020
Maowei Sea, China	Seawater	1.2e10.1 items/L, Ave: 4.5 ± 0.1 items/L	<0.25e5 mm	PES, PP, PE, PA, PS, POM, PU, PBT	Zhu et al., 2019
Mussel's farming in Jurujuba Cove	Seawater	16.4 items /m ³	<0.1 - 5 mm	PE, PP, EA	Castro et al., 2016
Fish farms in Mediterranean, Spain	Sediments	0-213		PE, PP, PA, Cellulose	Kruger et al., 2020
Eel culture stations, Shanghai	Seawater	1.0 ± 0.4 items/L	> 0,1-5 mm	PE, PP, EA	Lv et al 2020
Ma’an Archipelago marine ranching area,	Seawater	0.2 ± 0.1–0.6 ± 0.2 items/L	1-5 mm	PE, PP, PE-PP, PS and PA	Zhang et al., 2020
Weihai, China	Seawater	11.49 particles/m		PE, PP, PS	Zhang et al., 2021
Andratx, Spain	Seawater	0.27 ± 0.14 items/m ²		PE, PP, PS, PA	Capo et al., 2021

9 Monitoring recommendations for plastic litter present and future distribution trend documentation

Plastic pollution has been increasing globally over the last several decades. Although this form of pollution has become an issue of growing concern, leading to many local, regional, and international initiatives aiming to better understand and address it. Among the relevant sources, plastic equipment used in the fisheries and aquaculture industry may contribute to emissions of microplastics into the sea, which may potentially have negative consequences for the marine environment and living

organisms. A monitoring plan aiming at understanding the short- and long-term plastic litter fingerprint of such type of industry production is recommended. Several type of monitoring strategies are available nowadays. Overall, monitoring types can complement one another in the sense that the same observation and sampling strategy can be applied for different purposes. It is important to recognize that monitoring activities can be led and implemented by a variety of players not limited to aquaculture and IMTA managers but could include engagement and synergy with researchers, local authorities and community groups. An initial action should focus on “Baseline Mapping”. Such monitoring actions aim at establishing the benchmark levels for specific areas at a given time, which can be a starting point for studying spatial and temporal trends. Although the true background environmental level of litter and microplastics in the environment is zero, the term benchmark level is addressed here to describe the most historic state of litter and microplastics in the area meant for monitoring. This should be followed by a steadier and more permanent “Source and Surveillance” monitoring. Such assessment type aims at monitor potential point sources/specific pressures, including monitoring for determining local sources (e.g. melting sea ice, rivers, dumping sites, wastewater outlets, harbours etc.), or the transport of litter and microplastics into remote areas via long-range transport.

At the beginning of any monitoring operation, it is important to establish a benchmark level at selected sites that can be visited regularly. The results of subsequent surveys can be compared with the benchmark levels to see whether there has been a change in quantities, perhaps as the result of policy interventions in the area where the IMTA was installed, or because of a natural based event (e.g. storm, floodings or large-scale spill of litter or plastics). Over time, this can result in systematic trend monitoring or allow for the assessment of the impacts on litter and microplastics from a specific source or event as well as discriminate the plastics emission contribution from different sources. Because of the inherent variability in the abundance of litter and microplastics in all environmental compartments, high numbers of replicates and several years of sampling or observations may be required to detect a temporal trend with a sufficient statistical power.

A water sampling approach similar to the one used in ASTRAL is performed using harmonized methods like those implemented within this project and results reported in a standardized format as suggested by international harmonization committee like the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea-ICES (ICES, 2023) or the Oslo and Paris Conventions body – OSPAR to facilitate the data interoperability across different repositories. Water sampling should include litter and microplastics. Water sampling in inshore and coastal regions should be done using dedicated plastic free pumping systems targeting the surface water (1-7 m below the surface) and no deeper than the depth where the multitrophic species are deployed. Water sample should be passed through a sequential filtration system set with variable filter mesh size among those commercially available. In the present report 1 mm, 300 µm and 10 µm mesh size cascade is recommended. The volume of collected water should aim at obtaining a representative sample. Recommended volume range is 100-1000 L per sample. The use of replicates within the same sampling site is recommended to enable a good statistical treatment of the obtained data. Collection timing should consider the avoidance of algal bloom period in the investigated area. Wherever relevant sampling in rivers and estuarine ecosystems should be included for source monitoring, i.e. establish baseline levels of litter and put this result in relation to the observation of MPs in the nearby of IMTAs facilities. The inherent variability – and resulting statistical power - must be considered in the sampling strategy, regarding sampling frequencies. However, better knowledge of variability is an area of ongoing research. Therefore, in the absence of consolidated knowledge of variability, annual monitoring is recommended.

Furthermore, it is recommended that monitoring programs consider a joint water and sediment approach, where possible. The rationale for this recommendation is that water and sediment sampling can often be carried out in the same sampling campaign and provide complementary, but not overlapping, information on the status and trends of plastic contamination. When water and sediment sampling are combined, they provide the most complete picture of microplastics contamination of aquatic environments including potential exposure of organisms, from the benthic to the pelagic. Furthermore, water and sediment sampling provide different temporal perspectives on plastic pollution. Sediments provide a more spatially and temporally integrated signal of plastic contamination, whereas water samples can possibly track more rapid fluctuations. However, capturing the target water mass can be challenging, thus hydrodynamic processes in the area need to be well-known to interpret the results. Oceanographic data such as seawater temperature, currents, wind and waves distribution frequencies and intensities should be collected as important data for the integrative assessment. A variety of polymers can be found in sediment samples from beaches, whereas sampling in the sublittoral zone will target particles with a higher sinking rate with densities greater than seawater (e.g., PVC). Sampling of marine sediments allows for the detection and tracking of microplastics with a higher density than what is found in other compartments. It also allows for the detection of particles with changed density or settling properties resulting from biofouling. Microplastics in sediments should be monitored and reported in size categories.

As pointed out by the application of μ -FTIR analysis, the recourse of techniques such as vibrational spectroscopy-oriented methods able to report the results in term of MPs particles number, grain size, shape and mass are recommended for environment monitoring purpose. This way of data reporting may be useful to end users like the environmental modellers to refine particles distribution models. Depending in the current technologies' limitation, lower size classes ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) can provide additional data in areas where this is of interest i.e., toxicologists may understand the uptake risk for aquatic life and the associated biological consequences. In this context the future efforts should unveil the occurrence of MPS in the final seafood product. The results of the study performed within ASTRAL project show a diffuse occurrence of the microplastics in the nearby of the IMTA's installation however limited knowledge is available about how such type of emerging pollution affect the health status and ultimately quality of the farmed species (Lusher et al., 2017). Furthermore, sediments near rivers and estuarine ecosystems can improve the understanding of historic and current levels of deposition. The utilization of particle distribution models in aquatic environments is strongly advocated, particularly in the initial phase of establishing a sampling and monitoring grid. This aids in the anticipation of pollution hotspots, discerning contributions from both punctual and diffuse sources, and understanding the environmental dynamics of microplastics, encompassing factors such as sinking rates and interactions with biota. Furthermore, these models are instrumental in refining their efficacy as local, reliable data become available, facilitating the projection of present and future levels of contamination. A conventional approach involves employing an orthogonal transect sampling grid centred around aquaculture production sites, with sampling locations systematically positioned at increasing distances from the centre. The determination of each transect's reciprocal position is dictated by the outputs of the model.

Plastic pollution is a significant concern in aquaculture due to its potential negative impacts on aquatic ecosystems and marine life. The following mitigating actions may be considered in the future:

- **Reduce Plastic Usage:** Minimize the use of plastic materials wherever possible. This includes using alternatives such as biodegradable or reusable materials for containers, nets, ropes, and other equipment.

- **Proper Waste Management:** Implement proper waste management practices to ensure that any plastic waste generated during aquaculture operations is collected and disposed of responsibly. This may involve recycling or proper disposal methods to prevent plastic from entering waterways.
- **Regular Cleanup:** Conduct regular clean-up efforts in and around aquaculture facilities to remove any plastic debris that may have accumulated. This can help prevent plastics from entering water bodies and harming aquatic life.
- **Use of Eco-Friendly Alternatives:** Explore and adopt alternative materials that have minimal environmental impact. For example, using biodegradable fishing nets or compostable packaging materials can help reduce plastic pollution in aquaculture.
- **Education and Awareness:** Educate aquaculture practitioners, employees, and stakeholders about the importance of reducing plastic usage and the potential impacts of plastic pollution on aquatic ecosystems. Promote awareness campaigns and training programs to encourage responsible practices.
- **Investment in Research and Innovation:** Invest in research and development efforts to identify and develop innovative solutions for reducing plastic usage and pollution in aquaculture. This may involve developing new materials, technologies, or practices that are more sustainable and environmentally friendly.
- **Regulatory Measures:** Advocate for and comply with regulatory measures aimed at reducing plastic pollution in aquaculture. Support policies and initiatives that promote the use of sustainable materials and practices within the industry.
- **Collaboration and Partnerships:** Collaborate with other stakeholders, including government agencies, environmental organizations, and industry associations, to address plastic pollution in aquaculture collectively. Pooling resources and expertise can lead to more effective solutions.

By implementing these recommendations, aquaculture operations can help mitigate their contribution to plastic pollution and promote environmental sustainability in the industry.

References

- Acharya, S., Rumi, S. S., Hu, Y., & Abidi, N. (2021). Microfibers from synthetic textiles as a major source of microplastics in the environment: A review. *Textile Research Journal*, 91(17-18), 2136-2156.
- Aleynik, D., Dale, A. C., Porter, M., and Davidson, K. (2016). A high-resolution hydrodynamic model system suitable for novel harmful algal bloom modelling in areas of complex coastline and topography. *Harmful Algae* 53, 102–117. doi: 10.1016/j.hal.2015.11.012
- Beghetto, V., Gatto, V., Samiolo, R., Scolaro, C., Brahimi, S., Facchin, M., & Visco, A. (2023). Plastics today: Key challenges and EU strategies towards carbon neutrality: A review. *Environmental Pollution*, 122102.
- Brown, J., Carillo, L., Fernand, L., Horsburgh, K.J., Hill, A.E., Young, E.F., 2003. Observations of the physical structure and seasonal jet-like circulation of the Celtic Sea and St. George’s Channel of the Irish Sea. *Cont. Shelf Res.* 23, 533–561.
- Capo, X., Rubio, M., Solomando, A., Alomar, C., Compa, M., Sureda, A., & Deudero, S. (2021). Microplastic intake and enzymatic responses in *Mytilus galloprovincialis* reared at the vicinities of an aquaculture station. *Chemosphere*, 280, 130575.
- Castro, R.O., Silva, M.L., Marques, M.R.C., De Araújo, F.V., 2016. Evaluation of microplastics in Jurujuba Cove, Niter_oi, RJ, Brazil, an area of mussels farming. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 110 (1), 555e558.
- Chen, G., Feng, Q., Wang, J., 2020. Mini-review of microplastics in the atmosphere and their risks to humans. *Sci. Total Environ.* 703, 135504.
- Chen, G., Li, Y., & Wang, J. (2021). Occurrence and ecological impact of microplastics in aquaculture ecosystems. *Chemosphere*, 274, 129989.
- Chen, M., Jin, M., Tao, P., Wang, Z., Xie, W., Yu, X., et al., 2018. Assessment of microplastics derived from mariculture in Xiangshan Bay, China. *Environ. Pollut.* 242, 1146e1156.
- Chioatto, E., & Sospiro, P. (2023). Transition from waste management to circular economy: the European Union roadmap. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25(1), 249-276.
- Edwards A. 2018. Loch Linnhe ECE Estimates. Report Linnhe 2018 ECE 004.pdf for Scottish Sea Farms Laurel House Laurel Hill Business Park, Stirling, FK7 9JQ. 28pp. Downloaded from Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA)
- GESAMP (2016). “Sources, fate and effects of microplastics in the marine environment: part two of a global assessment” (Kershaw, P.J., and Rochman, C.M., eds). (IMO/FAO/UNESCO-IOC/UNIDO/WMO/IAEA/UN/ UNEP/UNDP Joint Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection). Rep. Stud. GESAMP No. 93, 220 p.
- Gomiero, A., Haave, M., Kögel, T., Bjorøy, Ø., Gjessing, M., Berg Lea, T., Horve, E. Martins, C., Olafsen, T. (2020). Tracking of Plastic emissions from aquaculture industry. NORCE Report n. 4 /2020. <https://www.fhf.no/prosjekter/prosjektbasen/901519/>
- Hardesty BD, Harari J, Isobe A, Lebreton L, Maximenko N, Potemra J, van Sebille E, Vethaak AD and Wilcox C (2017) Using Numerical Model Simulations to Improve the Understanding of Micro-plastic

Distribution and Pathways in the Marine Environment. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 4:30. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2017.00030

IBAL (Irish Business Against Litter) Yearly survey <https://ibal.ie/ibal-litter-survey-shows-most-beaches-not-clean/>

ICES, 2023 - Database on the Marine Environment (DOME). (year). ICES, Copenhagen, Denmark. <https://dome.ices.dk>

JPI Oceans program. "Fluxes and Fate of Microplastics in Northern European Waters – FACS" <https://jpi-oceans-facts.eu/>

Kern E. Kenyon, Stokes Drift for Random Gravity Waves, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, Vol 74, No 28, December 1969

Krüger, L., Casado-Coy, N., Valle, C., Ramos, M., Sanchez-Jerez, P., Gago, J., et al., 2020. Plastic debris accumulation in the seabed derived from coastal fish farming. *Environ. Pollut.* 257, 113336.

Lusher, A., Hollman, P., & Mendoza-Hill, J. (2017). Microplastics in fisheries and aquaculture: status of knowledge on their occurrence and implications for aquatic organisms and food safety. FAO.

Lv, W., Yuan, Q., He, D., Lv, W., Zhou, W., 2020. Microplastic contamination caused by different rearing modes of Asian swamp eel (*Monopterus albus*). *Aquacult. Res.* 51 (12), 5084e5095.

Miao, C., Zhang, J., Jin, R., Li, T., Zhao, Y., & Shen, M. (2023). Microplastics in aquaculture systems: occurrence, ecological threats and control strategies. *Chemosphere*, 139924.

Hazem Nagy, Kieran Lyons, Joseph McGovern, Diego Pereiro, Ioannis Mamoutos, et al.. RECENT PROGRESS IN DOWNSCALED LOCAL OCEAN FORECAST MODELS FOR IRISH MARITIME USERS. 9th EuroGOOS International conference, Shom; Ifremer; EuroGOOS AISBL, May 2021, Brest, France. pp.223-229. fahal-03328372v2

Lorna A. Taylor. 1997. Meteorological and Tidal Forcing of Loch Linnhe, a Scottish Sea-loch. Theses Submitted for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy, Department of Statistics and Modelling Science, University of Strathclyde.

Zhang, D., Cui, Y., Zhou, H., Jin, C., Yu, X., Xu, Y., et al., 2020b. Microplastic pollution in water, sediment, and fish from artificial reefs around the Ma'an Archipelago, Shengsi, China. *Sci. Total Environ.* 703, 134768.

Zhu, J., Zhang, Q., Li, Y., Tan, S., Kang, Z., Yu, X., et al., 2019. Microplastic pollution in the Maowei Sea, a typical mariculture bay of China. *Sci. Total Environ.* 658, 62e68.

Zhang, X., Li, S., Liu, Y., Yu, K., Zhang, H., Yu, H., & Jiang, J. (2021). Neglected microplastics pollution in the nearshore surface waters derived from coastal fishery activities in Weihai, China. *Science of The Total Environment*, 768, 144484.

van den Bremer T. S. and Breivik Ø. 2017. Stokes drift. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A.* 3762017010420170104 <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2017.0104>

Wang, W. X. (2023). Environmental toxicology of marine microplastic pollution. *Cambridge Prisms: Plastics*, 1, e10.

Wu, F., Wang, Y., Leung, J.Y.S., Huang, W., Zeng, J., Tang, Y., et al., 2020. Accumulation of microplastics in typical commercial aquatic species: a case study at a productive aquaculture site in China. *Sci. Total Environ.* 708, 135432.